

Studies on Formation Constants of some Metal(II) Chelates of *p*-Bromobenzoylthioacetone

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The stepwise formation constants of the complexes of *p*-bromobenzoylthioacetone with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have been determined potentiometrically using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-metric technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The effect of bromine substitution has been studied by comparing the formation constant data of the complexes with those of the corresponding complexes of benzoylthioacetone, i.e. the parent monothio- β -diketone of the ligand. The order of stabilities of the metal chelates has been evaluated.

A number of complexes of monothio- β -diketones (1; thioxo form) with metal ions of different classes have so far been reported¹⁻⁶ and their solution equilibria also studied potentiometrically²⁻⁴. Monothio- β -diketone generally behaves as an uni-negatively charged bidentate (O, S) chelating agent after deprotonation through its enol or enethiol form forming thereby a six-membered resonance stabilised chelate ring with the metal ions^{2,3}. However, no attempt appears to have been made so far to study the solution equilibria of the titled ligand (1) and its derived metal complexes—a work that can help to understand the effect of bromine substitution on the acid dissociation constant of the ligand and stability constant of its derived metal complexes when compared with those of its parent, i.e. benzoylthioacetone already reported^{2,3}. In the present communication we report the formation constants of the chelates of *p*-bromobenzoylthioacetone with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} in 75% aqueous dioxan (v/v) at a constant temperature of 30° and fixed ionic strength of 0.1M (KCl) as determined by Calvin-Bjerrum's⁷ pH-metric technique and as adopted by Irving and Rossotti^{2,3}.

Experimental

The ligand *p*-bromobenzoylthioacetone was synthesised in good yield by the Claisen condensation of *o*-ethylthioacetate with *p*-bromoacetophenone in the presence of ethereal suspension of sodamide by the reported method⁴. The crude product was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 90° (lit.⁴ 88–89°). *o*-Ethyl thioacetate was prepared

from acetonitrile by reacting it with ethanol, HCl and H₂S.

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. Purified dioxan¹⁰ and double-distilled water were used. Primary standard solution of the ligand solution was prepared in dioxan. Aqueous solutions of metal(II) chlorides were standardised¹¹. KOH solution was prepared in CO₂-free conductivity water and used to standardise HCl solution. KCl solution was prepared in 1:1 dioxan-water medium and was used to maintain the desired ionic strength.

A Systronic pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit) with combined glass and calomel electrodes, was used for pH measurements. The temperature was maintained constant at 30°.

Procedure: The following three mixtures were prepared: (i) 5 ml 0.4M HCl+5 ml KCl, (ii) mixture (i)+5 ml 0.02M ligand and (iii) mixture (ii) +5 ml 0.004M metal ion. Total volume in each case was maintained 50 ml such that the dioxan volume remained 70% and the ionic strength was kept at 0.1M (KCl). The mixtures were titrated (in duplicate) against 0.2M KOH solution and the pH was measured in O₂-free nitrogen atmosphere. The *B* values (pH meter reading) and the volume of alkali added was plotted in each case and referred to as (i) acid, (ii) ligand and (iii) complex titration curves, respectively.

Results and Discussion

From the acid and ligand titration curves, \bar{n}_A values at various *B*-values were calculated using the appropriate equation. Since the ligand is monoprotic due to the presence of a OH or SH group in its enol or enethiol form respectively, and there is no basic group to take up proton(s), so the value of the number of dissociable protons per ligand molecule (*Y*) was taken to be equal to one in the

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above calculation. The \bar{n}_A values increase with increasing B values showing increase in the degree of dissociation of the ligand. A plot of \bar{n}_A against B gave the formation curve of the ligand-proton complex from which pK_a of the ligand or its protonation constant ($K_1^H = 1/K_a$) was obtained by half-integral method, i.e. $\log K_1^H = pK_a = B$ at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. This was further corroborated by linear plot of $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B .

From the ligand and complex titration curves the values of \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the appropriate equations. Formation curves of the metal-ligand complexes were drawn by plotting \bar{n} vs pL for each of them. From these curves the stepwise formation constants of the each metal complex ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) were obtained by half-integral method, i.e. $\log K_1 = pL$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\log K_2 = pL$ at $\bar{n} = 1.5$. Since the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values was found to be very small so the same were refined by least-square treatment and the results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE AND OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANT DATA

Temp = 30°, $\mu = 0.1M$ KCl, Medium: 75% aqueous dioxan (v/v) ($\log K_1^H = pK_a = 10.12$)

Metal ions	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}
$\log K_1$	10.06	9.55	8.08	8.03
$\log K_2$	9.83	9.42	8.00	7.78
$\log \beta_2$	19.89	18.97	16.08	15.81

Monothio- β -diketones are known to exist as an equilibrium mixture of tautomeric enol and enethiol forms which interconvert rapidly by intra-molecular chelate proton transfer²⁻⁶. However, whether the ligand deprotonates through its enol or enethiol form, the anion (2) with negative charge delocalised over the whole ion, will be essentially the same.

The separation of ligand titration curve from acid titration curve begins only at $pH > 7$ and that it shifts to the right. But the separation of complex titration curve from the ligand titration curve begins at $pH \leq 4$ depending on the nature of the metal. These facts reveal that while the ligand has a very weak tendency to deprotonate, it has a very strong tendency to coordinate with the metal. These facts are also substantiated by very low dissociation constant of the ligand and very high formation constants

of its complexes. The higher value of K_a of the ligand ($pK_a = 10.12$) than that of its parent ($pK_a = 10.40, 10.43$)^{2,3} shows how deprotonation is favoured by the presence of Br-atom at the *para*-position of the benzoyl ring in benzoylthioacetone. This may probably be due to the electronegative nature of the substituent.

The values of \bar{n} range between zero and two, indicating the formation of ML_2 type of chelate analogous to the chelates of other monothio- β -diketones reported previously^{2,3}. Very small difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values shows that ML and ML_2 are formed almost simultaneously rather successively. The $\log \beta_2$ values of all the chelates are slightly less than those of the corresponding chelates of its parent (Cu, 20.22; Ni, 19.40; Zn, 16.50; Cd, 16.04)² indicating thereby the adverse effect of bromine substituent on the stabilities of the metal chelates. This may be attributed to the steric hindrance posed by the substituent together with increased acidic strength of the ligand.

The stability constants of the metal chelates follow the trend: $Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II}$. Though this sequence differs from the Mellor-Maley series² which has been found to hold almost universally for oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands or Irving-Williams natural order of stability^{1,8}, it is in conformity with the stability order reported for the chelates of these metals with several other monothio- β -diketones studied so far^{2,8}.

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